

PREDVIĐANJE CENA AKCIJA U AUTOMOBILSKOJ INDUSTRIJI KORIŠĆENJEM ALGORITMA DUBOKOG UČENJA

PREDICTING STOCK PRICES IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY WITH A DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHM

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Apstrakt: Ljudske kognitivne sposobnosti nisu u stanju da u potpunosti razumeju dinamiku svih trendova na finansijskim tržištima, kao što su ekonomski indikatori, performanse kompanija, sentiment vesti i drugi faktori. Srećom, mašine preuzimaju poslove koje su do skora obavljali investicioni analitičari obučeni za analizu kretanja cena na tržištima, što omogućava visokofrekventno trgovanje (HFT) i upotrebu sofisticiranih algoritama za predviđanje promena cena akcija na veoma kratkom vremenskom horizontu. Ovaj rad istražuje prediktivnu moć algoritma dubokog učenja – Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). U eksperimentalnom okviru analiza obuhvata pet kompanija iz automobilske industrije. Studija potvrđuje da je prediktivna moć LSTM-a velika, budući da je razlika između predviđene i stvarne cene akcija statistički beznačajna.

Ključne reči: finansijsko tržište, dubinsko učenje, duga kratkoročna memorija, automobilska industrija

Abstract: Human cognitive capacities are unable to fully understand the dynamics of all financial market trends such as economic indicators, company performance, news sentiment, and more. Luckily, machines have been taking over the human-centric job related to stock market movements analyses, thus allowing for the high-frequency trading (HFT) and the use of sophisticated algorithms to predict stock price movements on a very short timescale. This paper investigates the prediction power of a deep learning algorithm – Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). For the experimental setting, the analysis includes five companies from the automotive industry. This study confirms that the predicting power of LSTM is large since the difference between predicted and real stock price is statistically insignificant.

Keywords: stock market; deep learning; long short-term memory; automotive industry.

1. INTRODUCTION

Prediction of stock price movement has been a 'holy grail' of financial science and practice for decades now. Knowing the future at stock exchange might help investors make adequate investment decisions, hedge against numerous risks, allow policymakers to establish policies to create efficient markets and fully optimize resource allocation. However, the complexity of market movements makes it difficult if not impossible to make even day-to-day predictions (Milosavljevic et al., 2024). It has been an age-old wisdom that stocks follow 'random walks' (Fama, 1995), meaning that any predictions are merely a clairvoyant job.

Human cognitive capacities are unable to fully understand the dynamics of all market trends such as economic indicators, company performance, news sentiment, and more. Luckily, machines have been taking over the human-centric job related to stock market movements analyses (Patel et al., 2015), thus allowing for the high-frequency trading and the use of sophisticated algorithms to predict stock price movements on a very short timescale. This should, however, be taken with considerations. Novel studies imply 'that that with the current technology of AI, it is too soon to claim AI can beat the stock markets' (Mokhtari, Yen & Liu, 2021). Finally, stock market modeling and predictions have not been solely 'human' and will never probably be solely 'machine-conducted' (Lu, Poon & Khushi, 2024).

A number of machine learning algorithms, and particularly the deep ones, have been used to project the movements in stock prices (Shah et al., 2019). This paper investigates the prediction power of a specific deep learning algorithm – Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). This algorithm has already been widely used in the concurrent literature (Gülmez, 2023).

For the experimental setting, the analysis includes five companies from the automotive industry: Tesla Inc. [TSLA], General Motors Company [GM], Ford Motor Company [F], Rivian Automotive Inc. [RIVN] & Lotus Company [LOT]. The results indicate that LSTM has a solid power in predicting stock price movement allowing for appropriate decisions be investors, hedge funds, and other market players.

The remainder of the paper is organized in the following order: Section 2 explains the methodology of this study including the sampling procedure, brief explanation of the long-short-term memory as an algorithm, and an experimental environment.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this section we elaborate on the methodology of this study. First, we elaborate the rationale behind the selection of automotive industry and five companies selected for

the sample. Then, we briefly explain the logics of LSTM. Finally, we depict the experimental setup for this particular neuron network.

2.1. Sample

For the sample, we selected five companies from the automotive industry. In 2023, the global car production has hit 76 million units with a substantial increase from 2022 of 10.2% (ACEA, 2024). Not surprisingly, many countries have made their automotive industry an industry of strategic importance (Halili, 2020).

On the one hand, the automotive industry is characterized by a high degree of standardization and saturation (Simonazzi et al., 2020). Market growth, strategic importance and high saturation make this industry the perfect candidate to test predictability of stock price movements as the stock price movements is lower in saturated industry with many incumbent players compared to dynamic industries. On the other hand, predictability is slightly jeopardized by the emergence of new technologies (Yeung, 2023) and new players and automotive industry transformation (Hoeft, 2021).

For the experiment on stock price prediction, we selected five companies: Tesla Inc., General Motors Company, Ford Motor Company, Rivian Automotive Inc. & Lotus Company.

2.2. Long short-term memory

Long short-term memory (LSTM) is a class of recursive neural networks built to overcome the gradient vanishing or exploding problem by intelligently forgetting past irrelevant information. LSTM networks contain memory cells that maintain state information over time using memory and output units to regulate and manage information flow. These networks employ three types of gates: forget, input, and output gates. Forget gates eliminate irrelevant past information, preserving only what is necessary for the current step. Input gates manage the information entering the current network state. The forget gate's old information and the input gate's new information are combined into the cell state vector. The output gate generates the network's final output at the current layer, which represents the predicted value calculated by the model for the current pass (Mehtab et al. 2021).

2.3. Experimental environment

The experimental environment was replicated from the Milosavljevic et al (2023) study. The data was split into train and test parts by using the reshape function. After pre-processing the data by using min-max scaler, we made a sequential model in 'Tensorflow' with 50 neurons in the first, and the additional 50 neurons in the second layer. Also, we added two dense (output) layers, one with 10 and the other with a single neuron. To

compile the model, we used the Adam compiler (Kingma and Ba, 2014). To check how well the model was trained, we utilized mean square error for a loss function (Wu et al. 2018).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, we conducted pre-analysis. The time series were decomposed with regards to the trend, cyclicity, and irregular movements (Qi & Zhang, 2008). The results for Dickey-Fuler test are presented in Table 1.

Table 3. Dickey-Fuler Test

Item	TSLA	GM	F	RIVN	LOT
Test statistics	-1.2922	-2.5870	-2.5751	-5.5471	-2.9989
p-value	0.6327	0.0957	0.0982	0.000002	0.0349
#Lags used	28.0000	19.0000	18.0000	18.0000	19.0000
# of Observ.	2588	2597	2598	619	749
Crit. Val. 1%	-3.4329	-3.4329	-3.4329	-3.4409	-3.4391
Crit. Val. 5%	-2.8626	-2.8626	-2.8626	-2.8662	-2.8654
Crit. Val. 10%	-2.5674	-2.5674	-2.5674	-2.5693	-2.5688

For the main analysis, we ran the model on the observed set of companies using 'batch_size' (=32) and 'epochs' (=10). The results are displayed in Figure 1.

(5) LOT

Figure 1: Predicted stock price movement
Source: Authors' calculations

Finally, we tested the predicting power of the model (displayed in Table 2).

Table 4. Predicted vs actual price of stocks

Company	Predicted value	Actual value
TESL	185.7212	176.75
GM	45.1862	43.09
F	12.1001	11.68
RIVN	10.2908	10.42
LOT	8.9976	10.9

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study we analyzed predictability of stock price movements for five companies in the automotive industry. Five technical attributes were used to create neural model based on LSTM approach. The predictive power of the model is moderately high. This can be useful for investors, brokers and other stock market players, particularly those basing their trading strategies on algorithmic trading.

Accurately predicting stock prices remains a complex task due to the inherent volatility and stochastic nature of financial markets. Although machine learning models can provide valuable insights, their predictions are not always precise and must be interpreted with caution, taking into account the multitude of external factors that may influence stock price movements. In line with this, our study is subject to several limitations. First, the analysis is restricted to five global automotive companies, which may partially simplify the prediction task. Consequently, the generalizability of the results to other industries with higher levels of uncertainty and volatility remains limited.

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